

WATER ABSORPTION IN CARBON AND
GLASS FIBRE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Experiments in which epoxy resins, and an epoxy copolymer, and also carbon and glass pultrusions made with these resins, were exposed to water, showed that expanding monomers reduced the water absorption of the resins and composites. Most of the water in the resins seemed to segregate into disc-shaped regions. In the composites, especially the glass reinforced ones, the water tended to concentrate at the fibre-matrix interface. A new analysis of diffusivity which can take into account voids as well as the interphasial region between the fibres and the matrix strongly suggests that, with these pultrusions at least, (which had void volumes of about one sixtieth of the fibre volume) the most effective conducting path for water was provided by the voids, rather than the interphase.

INTRODUCTION

The absorption of water by structural composites, and the resin matrices used for them, has been much studied because it can result in a significant increase in weight of the structure, and some loss in mechanical properties.

In the case of carbon fibre composites the effects due to water are mostly reversible [1,2], but very long exposures (> 2000 hr at 71°C and 95% relative humidity (RH)) can cause resin cracking [3]. In the case of glass fibre composites, the fibres themselves may also be weakened by the exposure: loss of fibre strength has been observed after immersion in water at 80°C [4]. Kevlar fibres are also affected by water; the fibres absorb water, and this accounts for the greater water uptake of the Kevlar composites [5], as compared with glass and carbon. Water can thus affect the fibre and the resin. In the case of the resin, the absorption follows simple laws. It is generally Fickian, and in humid air obeys a simple relationship:

$$M_s = a(RH)^b \quad (1)$$

where M_s is the saturated weight gain of the polymer as a fraction of the original weight, a and b are constants, and, for RH given fractionally, a is in the range 5-10% for epoxies and b is between 1 and 3. Both a and b depend on the resin; a is only very slightly affected by temperature. Diffusion constants depend on temperature; typical values can range from 1.6 to 4 $\mu\text{m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$, for neat epoxies at 100°C: they obey the Arrhenius equation with activation energies typically in the range 43-50 kJmol^{-1} [6,7].

Little is known about the effect of water on the special expanding monomers used to reduce the cure shrinkage of epoxies. Dinorbornene spiro orthocarbonate has been most used to improve composite toughness [8], but dicyclohexane spiro orthocarbonate, in which the norbornene groups are replaced by cyclohexanes, has also been tested and found to be effective in improving toughness [9].

In this paper the effects of moisture on spiro-epoxy controlled shrinkage copolymers, and their composites, are examined. In addition to measuring water uptake, the dielectric constants of the materials were measured. The spiro orthocarbonate produces carbonyl groups when the rings are opened during polymerization. This will affect the dipole moment of the resin, and will act as possible extra hydrogen bonding sites for water. Thus capacitance measurements should give some insight into the processes taking place during water absorption. Although data are available on dielectric constants of resins, there does not appear to have been a systematic study of the effect of water on them.

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

Two diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A type resins were used for this study. One was a low viscosity resin, Shell Epon 815, which contains a reactive diluent, butyl glycidyl ether, and has a viscosity of 5-7 poises at 25°C. The other, DOW DER 332, contains no diluent, and has a viscosity of 40-60 poises at 25°C. Copolymers were made with the DER 332 and dinorbornene spiro orthocarbonate.

The resins were cured with triethylene tetramine (TETA) and Shell Anchor 1115 and 1171, and given the curing treatments shown in Table 1. When the spiro was used, this had to be finely ground in order to disperse it in the resin, which was heated to 60°C in a vacuum oven, and then cooled to 40°C for the addition of the curing agent. The mixtures were poured into oblong aluminum molds with cross-sections 25.4 mm x 1 mm, and 400 mm long.

Carbon and E-glass pultrusions were made with the resins by immersing hanks of the fibres in the resins at room temperature until they were thoroughly wetted, then pulling them inside rectangular molds. Fibre volume fraction was controlled by the amount of fibres used for the pultrusion process. The molds containing the pultrusions were then cured as indicated in Table 1. (Anchor 1171 was used as curing agent for the glass fibre pultrusions because Anchor 1115 (used in the previous work on toughness etc. [8], of carbon fibre pultrusions) appeared to react with the sizing on the glass fibres, producing bubbles. Anchor 1171 did not have this problem.)

The specimens were conditioned by immersing them in distilled water and keeping them under conditions of fixed humidity. In the immersion tests, a beaker, immersed in a constant temperature oil bath, was half filled with water, and had the specimen placed in it. For the relative

TABLE I

Resins Used, Curing Conditions, and Saturated Water Contents After Immersion

Resin	Curing Agent Type	Agent Amount %	Cure °C	hr	Post Cure °C	hr	M _s (%by weight) [†]	
							23°C	100°C
EPON 815	TETA	10	60	4	110	16	2.8	3.5
DER 332	Anchor 1115	7	80	4	130	20	2.7	3.0
SPIRO *	Anchor 1115	7	80	4	130	20	2.1	2.5

*DER 332 with 5% dinorbornene spiro orthocarbonate added.

†Results at intermediate temperatures fitted a linear relationship; standard deviations were 7% or less.

humidity tests, the specimen was placed in a rack above the surface of a saturated solution of a salt in a closed container. The container was kept in an oven at the appropriate temperatures and humidities. Different salts were used to give different humidities.

Before conditioning, and periodically during the conditioning, the specimens were weighed, and had their densities and dielectric properties measured. The densities were measured using the pycnometer method described in ASTM D792-66 (for plastics; distilled water was used as the displacement medium).

The dielectric constants ϵ' and dielectric losses, ϵ'' were measured by placing the resin or composite between aluminum foil electrodes in a shielded assembly, and measuring the capacitance of the assembly using a GenRad model GR 1688 Precision LC Digibridge operated at a frequency of 1 kHz. To ensure good contact between the foil electrodes and the sample, the foil was backed by silicone rubber sheets 10 mm thick, and pressure was applied using a 3.5 kg weight.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Water Absorption and Diffusion Constant

The water absorption obeyed Fick's Law. Fig. 1 shows the weight gain, expressed as a fraction of total weight, for EPON 815, and glass reinforced EPON 815 after immersion in water for various lengths of time. The initial part of the plots, vs $\sqrt{\text{time}}$ was linear. Similar results were obtained when the composites were exposed to different temperature and relative humidities.

Fig. 1. Water absorption of glass-EPON 815 composites.

Fig. 2. Water absorption of free fibres at 98% RH and 23°C.

With the resins, about 10-20% less water was absorbed at 98% RH than when immersed in water at the same temperature. The resins did not obey Henry's Law. Instead, the saturated weight gain, M_S , obeyed a power law. For the EPON 815

$$M_S \approx 2.8 (RH)^{1.4} \quad (2)$$

where M_S is expressed as a percentage of the dry weight and RH is expressed fractionally. M_S was greatest for EPON 815 and least for the spiro, Table 1. In the case of the DER 332 there was loss of weight once saturation was attained after immersion at 100°C. M_S increased about 20% as temperature increased from 23 to 100°C. The diffusion constant, D_p , obeyed the Arrhenius equation. For the EPON 815.

$$D_p \approx 550 \text{ RHe}^{-E/RT} \text{ mm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1} \quad (3)$$

with an activation energy of 48 kJmol^{-1} . The DER 332 and the copolymer obeyed equation 3 with $E = 41 \text{ kJmol}^{-1}$.

The fibres absorbed some water also, and behaved as though they obeyed Fick's Law. Fig. 2 shows the results of exposing them to 98% RH.

With the glass fibre composites, those with EPON 815 as matrix behaved very simply, the water absorption being given by a rule of mixtures:

$$V_{WC} = V_f V_{Wf} + V_p V_{Wp} \quad (4)$$

where the V 's are volume fractions and the subscripts c, f, p, w refer to composite, fibre, polymer and water respectively. Fig. 3 shows the results for EPON 815 for all immersion and humidity tests at 23°C, 40°C, 75°C and 100°C. Relative absorption = V_{WC}/V_{Wp} . Fig. 4 shows the results at 23°C

Fig. 3. Relative water absorption for glass-EPON 815 composites 23-100°C.

Fig. 4. Relative water absorption for glass-epoxies: inset is absorption by fibres and resins alone.

for EPON 815 for 97% RH (●) and immersion (Δ) and for the DER 332 (o) and the copolymer (spiro:□) for immersion. The DER 332 and spiro composites did not fit equation 3. With the carbon fibre composites, water absorption, fig. 5, was only very approximately given by equation 3. The relative diffusivities ($=D_C/D_D$) of all composites, under all conditions, however, fitted a straight line when plotted vs $\sqrt{V_f}$, see fig. 6.

Dielectric Properties

The permittivities (ϵ') and loss factors ($\tan \delta$) of the resins were linear functions of the amount of water present. Thus

$$\epsilon_{ps} = (1+V_w \Delta) \epsilon_p \tag{5}$$

where ϵ_p represents the permittivity or $\tan \delta$ of the dry resins, and ϵ_{ps} that of the saturated resins. Δ values for permittivities are given in Table 2 for the three resins tested.

Glass fibres in the resins increased the permittivities linearly with fibre volume, for EPON 812, fig 7 but non-linearly with the DER 332 and the spiro, figs. 8 and 9. Similar results were noted with $\tan \delta$, figs. 10 and 11. As expected on the basis of its high dielectric constant and loss, the water markedly increased the dielectric properties of the reinforced EPON 815. However, the increases were anomalously great in the case of the DER 332 and the spiro.

Fig. 5. Relative water absorption for carbon-epoxies: inset is absorption by fibres and resins alone.

Fig. 6. Relative diffusivities of all composites tested, 23-100°C, immersion and 30-98% RH.

TABLE 2

Data From Dielectric Experiments on the Resins

Resin	Δ	Δ_s	Δ_r	Δ_d	% water in incipient cracks
EPON 815	9.5	2.6	5.3	12.6	75
DER 332	10.1	2.6	5.7	13.9	73
SPIRO	8.3	2.6	5.7	13.9	60

The dielectric constants of all the dry composites obeyed a mixture rule for inclusions in the form of needles [10]:

$$1 - V_f = \frac{\epsilon_f - \epsilon_c}{\epsilon_f - \epsilon_p} \left\{ \frac{\epsilon_f + 5\epsilon_p}{\epsilon_f + 5\epsilon_c} \right\}^{2/3} \quad (6)$$

The curves in fig. 12 were drawn using equation 6. The results fit the lines within one standard deviation or better.

DISCUSSION

The Resins

The resins themselves showed considerable differences in their water absorption characteristics. EPON 815 absorbed about 2.8% by weight of water at 23°C, rising to 3.5% at 100°C. The copolymer (spiro) absorbed 2.1% and 2.5% at those temperatures, while the DER 332 gave intermediate results.

Fig. 7. Wet and dry permittivities of glass-EPON 815 composites.

Fig. 8. Wet and dry permittivities of glass-DER 332 and glass-spiro composites.

The dielectric constants of the resins increased significantly (and linearly) with water content, equation 5. Since the volume fraction of water (V_w) attainable at equilibrium is quite small ($\neq 0.04$) with these resins, for temperatures in the range 20-100°C this strongly suggests that the water is not completely dissolved in the resin. (If it were dissolved it would contribute an insignificant amount to the dielectric constant, since the dielectric constant of single water molecules is low). Instead, some of the water is probably segregated in the form of spheres, or other shapes. For example, for water in the form of rods or needles we could use equation 6. This reduces, for $V_w < 0.04$, to equation 5 with $\Delta = \Delta_r$ where

$$\Delta_r = 3(\epsilon_w - \epsilon_p)(\epsilon_w + 5\epsilon_p) / \epsilon_p(13\epsilon_w + 5\epsilon_p) \quad (7)$$

Similarly for spheres $\Delta = \Delta_s$ in equation 6 and

$$\Delta_s = 3(\epsilon_w - \epsilon_p) / (\epsilon_w + 2\epsilon_p) \quad (8)$$

while for discs [10]

$$\Delta_d = (\epsilon_w - \epsilon_p) (2\epsilon_w + \epsilon_p) / 3\epsilon_w \epsilon_p \quad (9)$$

Values for Δ_s etc. are compared with experimental Δ 's in table 2. It can be seen that Δ_d is always the largest, Δ_s is always the smallest, and that the experimental values lie between Δ_r and Δ_d . Thus it is highly probable that some of the water has segregated as discs. The rest probably dissolved. On this basis we estimate the last column in table 2. Since cracking has been observed when epoxy resins were immersed in very hot water for long periods [11], these disc-like regions are identified as incipient cracks.

Fig. 9. Wet and dry dielectric losses of glass-EPON 815 composites.

Fig. 10. Wet and dry dielectric losses of glass-DER 332 composites.

Water absorption from the vapour did not obey Henry's Law. This result is in agreement with other workers [6]. The diffusion constant varied with temperature, according to Arrhenius, with an activation energy of 41 (DER 332 and spiro) and 48 kJmol^{-1} (EPON 815).

The Composites

These also obeyed Fick's Law. However, simple mixture rules were not observed for all the composites: agreement was fairly good for the EPON 815, but large deviations were observed with the DER 332 and the copolymer with both glass and carbon fibres. This is probably due to segregation of water at the interfaces between fibres and matrix. In support of this, microscopic observations showed spaces between fibres and matrix in samples which had absorbed 2-5% of water.

The very high $\tan \delta$ values for the composites made with DER 332 and the copolymer (figs. 10 and 11) indicate that free water was not only present, but that it was conducting. This could be due to the presence of F^-

or BF_4^- from the curing agent. It is possible also that incipient matrix cracking generated extensive conducting paths.

The diffusivities of the composites, fig. 6, did not fit the relationship suggested by Shen and Springer [12]. The model they used was somewhat simplistic, since it involved straight-line flow paths. In addition there appear to be errors in their integration. A new analysis has been carried out recently [13]. For fibres with a diffusivity D_f , and diameter $2r$, surrounded by an interphasial region thickness t , with a diffusivity D_i , in a polymer matrix with diffusivity D_p we find approximately that

Fig. 11. Wet and dry dielectric losses of glass-Spiro composites.

Fig. 12. Dry dielectric constant and losses of glass fibre composites.

$$D_c/D_p = \left[\frac{D_p}{D_p - D_f} \left\{ \frac{2}{\sqrt{1-c^2}} \tan^{-1} \sqrt{\frac{1+c}{1-c}} - \frac{\pi}{2} \right\} + \frac{D_p t}{D_p(a-t) + D_i t} + \frac{a-r-t}{a} \right]^{-1} \quad (10)$$

where

$$c = r(D_p - D_f) / (D_p(a-t) + D_i t) \quad (11)$$

and a is the size of the square unit cell of considered. Thus $V_f = 4a^2/\pi r^2$.

These equations do not give a linear plot for D_c vs $\sqrt{V_f}$ (see fig. 6). (These approximate equations give results which are indistinguishable from an exact analysis requiring numerical integration).

However, a similar analysis, but with voids which have enhanced conductivity for water (replacing an interphase having enhanced conductivity) gives the almost straight line shown in fig. 6. Since this fits the results so well, it is concluded that, with these composites, which had void volume fractions of about 0.0167 V_f , the void diffusivity dominated the polymer diffusivity. The observation that the carbon and glass results both fit the same line supports this interpretation, since the interphases will be completely different in these cases.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The addition of expanding monomers reduces the water absorption of epoxy resins and of composites made therefrom.
2. Most of the water in epoxy resins probably segregates into disc-shaped regions and this can lead to cracking of the resin.
3. With composites water segregates to the fibre-matrix interface when glass fibres are used, but such segregation is less marked with carbon fibres.
4. The main conducting path for water in pultrusions is provided by the voids. These constitute a "diffusion path" which has a diffusion coefficient of about 15 times that of the resin. Enhanced diffusion in the interphase appears to be less effective.

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